

Minimum Complexity Memristive-Friendly Echo State Network

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Abstract. We propose a novel Memristive-Friendly Echo State Network (MF-ESN) architecture, named MF-RingESN, that leverages structured connectivity patterns derived from minimum complexity principles. Specifically, the proposed model adopts the Simple Cycle Reservoir (SCR) topology within a memristive-friendly computational framework. We evaluate our approach on a diverse suite of time series classification and regression tasks. Our results demonstrate that the MF-RingESN maintains or improves upon the performance of the original MF-ESN while significantly reducing the complexity of the reservoir structure, thereby enabling more efficient and potentially more sustainable neuromorphic computing implementations.

Keywords: Memristive computing · Echo state network · Minimum complexity · Simple cycle reservoir.

1 Introduction

The exponential growth of artificial intelligence and deep learning applications has brought remarkable advancements but also raised concerns about energy consumption and environmental sustainability [16,14]. As such, building sustainable AI is becoming an increasingly important goal. Neuromorphic computing offers a compelling solution by emulating the mechanisms of biological brains to achieve efficient and scalable learning [5]. Among neuromorphic technologies, memristive devices [18] have gained attention due to their ability to mimic synaptic behavior through nanoscale physics, offering in-memory computing capabilities and energy efficiency [10]. These devices exhibit nonlinear and short-term memory dynamics that make them promising candidates for building the next generation of efficient and intelligent hardware.

From a theoretical computational perspective, Reservoir Computing (RC) is a framework particularly suitable for neuromorphic implementation [15,11]. In RC, the recurrent component of the network (the reservoir) is not trained; instead, only a linear readout is learned [8,17]. This allows the use of fixed physical substrates, such as memristive networks, as computational reservoirs,

thereby leveraging their inherent dynamics. Recently, a software-based model called Memristive-Friendly Echo State Network (MF-ESN) has been proposed to emulate the behavior of memristive reservoirs [12]. The MF-ESN captures the essential dynamics of memristive systems while preserving the training simplicity of traditional ESNs.

In this paper, we investigate how to reduce the complexity of the MF-ESN architecture by drawing inspiration from the Simple Cycle Reservoir (SCR) model [13], which has been shown to match the performance of standard ESNs with drastically reduced structural complexity. By applying the SCR topology to the MF-ESN framework, we propose the MF-RingESN model, characterized by an annular, deterministic reservoir connectivity. We evaluate the performance of MF-RingESN on various time series tasks and compare it to the original MF-ESN and other ESN variants, demonstrating its potential for complexity reduction without sacrificing accuracy.

The rest of this paper is organized as follows. In Section 2 we introduce the relevant concepts of the Echo State Network model and the related minimum complexity design strategy. Then, in Section 3, we introduce the memristive-friendly design and our proposed approach based on cycle reservoirs. Our experimental analysis is given in Section 4, while Section 5 concludes the paper.

2 Echo State Networks and minimum complexity

An Echo State Network (ESN) [6,7] is a type of recurrent neural network that consists of an input layer, a reservoir (i.e., a fixed dynamical system), and a trainable linear readout. Given input $\mathbf{u}(t) \in \mathbb{R}^{N_u}$, the reservoir state $\mathbf{h}(t) \in \mathbb{R}^{N_h}$ is updated as:

$$\mathbf{h}(t+1) = (1 - \alpha)\mathbf{h}(t) + \alpha \tanh(\mathbf{W}_{in}\mathbf{u}(t+1) + \mathbf{W}_{res}\mathbf{h}(t) + \mathbf{b}) \quad (1)$$

where α is the leaking rate, \mathbf{W}_{in} is the input matrix, \mathbf{W}_{res} is the recurrent matrix, and \mathbf{b} is the bias vector. The output is computed as:

$$\mathbf{y}(t+1) = \mathbf{W}_{out}\mathbf{h}(t+1) \quad (2)$$

where \mathbf{W}_{out} is the only trainable component, typically trained with ridge regression. As is typical in RC, matrices \mathbf{W}_{in} and \mathbf{W}_{res} are randomly initialized and then rescaled accordingly to match the characteristics of the task at hand.

In a RingESN (similar to the Simple Cycle Reservoir [13]), the matrix \mathbf{W}_{res} is structured as a cyclic matrix with one non-zero entry per row, $r > 0$, precisely on the subdiagonal, and on the top right corner, while all other entries are zero, as in (3), i.e.:

$$\mathbf{W}_{res} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & \dots & 0 & r \\ r & 0 & 0 & \dots & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & r & 0 & \dots & 0 & 0 \\ \vdots & \ddots & \ddots & \ddots & \vdots & \vdots \\ 0 & \dots & 0 & r & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \dots & 0 & 0 & r & 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (3)$$

This reduces reservoir complexity to a deterministic ring topology.

Hyperparameters of ESN/RingESN include: number of units, leaking rate, spectral radius of \mathbf{W}_{res} , input scaling of the matrix \mathbf{W}_{in} , and bias scaling of the vector \mathbf{b} .

3 MF-RingESN: the proposed model

The MF-ESN model [12] modifies the reservoir dynamics of a standard ESN to emulate memristive behavior. Its reservoir state update is governed by:

$$\mathbf{h}(t+1) = \gamma \mathbf{h}(t) + \Delta t [K_p(\mathbf{x}(t+1)) - \text{diag}(K_p(\mathbf{x}(t+1)) + K_d(\mathbf{x}(t+1)))\mathbf{h}(t)], \quad (4)$$

where K_p and K_d are exponential functions encoding potentiation and depression dynamics, and Δt is a discretization step. The potentiation and depression rates are defined as follows:

$$K_p(x) = K_{p_0} \cdot e^{\eta_p x} \quad (5)$$

$$K_d(x) = K_{d_0} \cdot e^{-\eta_d x} \quad (6)$$

K_{p_0} , η_p , K_{d_0} and η_d are memristive-based parameters that are determined by their physical plausibility, namely, $K_{p_0} = 0.0001$, $\eta_p = 10$, $K_{d_0} = 0.5$, and $\eta_d = 1$, as in [9].

The vector $\mathbf{x}(t+1)$ is the rescaled effective input combining the input, reservoir, and bias, computed as follows:

$$\mathbf{x}(t+1) = \text{RESCALE}(\mathbf{W}_{in}\mathbf{u}(t+1) + \mathbf{W}_{res}\mathbf{h}(t) + \mathbf{b}), \quad (7)$$

where the RESCALE function is defined as:

$$\text{RESCALE}(z) = \frac{b-a}{1+\exp(-zs)} + a, \quad (8)$$

where $a = 0.35$ and $b = 1.15$ are fixed parameters as in [12], whereas s is a hyperparameter that tunes the nonlinearity of the transformation. The output is again computed via a linear readout trained by ridge regression.

We define MF-RingESN as an MF-ESN model where the reservoir weight matrix \mathbf{W}_{res} is structured according to a simple ring topology of (3). The rest of the model follows the MF-ESN formulation: the dynamics are computed via the discretized memristive equation, and only the linear readout is trained. The hyperparameters of MF-ESN and MF-RingESN include classical RC hyperparameters and add others: γ (stabilizer), exponent base p (for the RESCALE function), and time step Δt .

4 Experiments

Model selection was performed using Bayesian Optimization over the search space shown in Table 4, using 100 trials per model per task. Each trial was

evaluated 5 times on the validation data, and the best configuration was tested 5 times on the test set. We used datasets from the Aeon library¹ with the default splits, further dividing the training set into 80% train and 20% validation.

Group	Parameter	Min	Max	Step	Sampling
ESN & Ring	units	50	200	10	–
	leaky	0.01	0.99	0.05	linear
	input_scaling	0.01	10	–	log
	bias_scaling	0.001	1	–	log
	spectral_radius	0.01	0.99	0.05	linear
MF-ESN & MF-Ring	units	50	200	10	–
	input_scaling	0.1	10	–	log
	memory_factor	0.01	0.99	0.05	linear
	bias_scaling	0.001	1	–	log
	gamma	0.1	1	0.05	linear
	p	1	10	1	linear
	dt	0.0001	0.1	–	log
Fixed physical parameters (MF-ESN & MF-Ring)		<i>(fixed)</i>			
	alpha	1	1	–	–
	kp0	0.0001	0.0001	–	–
	kd0	0.5	0.5	–	–
	etap	10	10	–	–
	etad	1	1	–	–
Readout ridge regularizer (all models)		0.001	1	–	log

Table 1. Search space for the Model Selection through Bayesian Search.

Table 2 and Table 3 report the performance of ESN, RingESN, MF-ESN, and MF-RingESN on classification and regression tasks, respectively. The reported performance is computed in terms of accuracy, for the classification tasks, and in terms of root mean squared error (RMSE), for the regression ones.

Experimental results confirm that Ring-based models perform comparably to standard ones. In classification (Table 2), MF-RingESN achieved competitive or superior accuracy in several cases (e.g., Coffee, GunPoint, EMOPain). In regression (Table 3), MF-RingESN matched or outperformed MF-ESN on Covid3Month and NewsHeadlineSentiment.

Figures 1 and 2 display critical difference plots [2], showing no statistically significant difference between the models. This corroborates the potential of Ring-based architectures as lower-complexity alternatives to traditional ESNs and MF-ESNs. We can conclude that it is possible to substantially reduce the architectural complexity of memristive-inspired models, as MF-ESN, without compromising predictive performance, reinforcing the practicality of simpler, more efficient designs in neuromorphic and energy-constrained settings.

¹ <https://www.aeon-toolkit.org/en/stable/>

Classification Task	ESN	MF-ESN	RingESN	MF-RingESN
Coffee	0.764 ± 0.140	0.986 ± 0.018	1.000 ± 0.000	1.000 ± 0.000
Wafer	0.995 ± 0.001	0.991 ± 0.001	0.995 ± 0.000	0.988 ± 0.001
SyntheticControl	0.983 ± 0.002	0.991 ± 0.005	0.993 ± 0.004	0.985 ± 0.002
ArticularyWordRecognition	0.970 ± 0.004	0.936 ± 0.012	0.967 ± 0.007	0.916 ± 0.004
JapaneseVowels	0.986 ± 0.006	0.991 ± 0.002	0.986 ± 0.001	0.989 ± 0.002
ItalyPowerDemand	0.870 ± 0.007	0.918 ± 0.007	0.871 ± 0.002	0.907 ± 0.012
GunPoint	0.919 ± 0.014	0.855 ± 0.028	0.931 ± 0.007	0.959 ± 0.021
ECG5000	0.924 ± 0.001	0.930 ± 0.000	0.930 ± 0.002	0.931 ± 0.001
Epilepsy	0.903 ± 0.006	0.851 ± 0.007	0.893 ± 0.003	0.868 ± 0.016
EMOPain	0.686 ± 0.061	0.703 ± 0.040	0.641 ± 0.092	0.761 ± 0.056
FordA	0.650 ± 0.010	0.654 ± 0.011	0.666 ± 0.009	0.535 ± 0.003
ChlorineConcentration	0.616 ± 0.008	0.587 ± 0.002	0.658 ± 0.012	0.587 ± 0.001
Worms	0.308 ± 0.006	0.355 ± 0.013	0.307 ± 0.007	0.330 ± 0.012

Table 2. Classification accuracy (mean ± std).

Regression Task	ESN	MF-ESN	RingESN	MF-RingESN
FloodModeling1	0.008 ± 0.000	0.016 ± 0.001	0.008 ± 0.000	0.019 ± 0.000
FloodModeling3	0.009 ± 0.000	0.019 ± 0.001	0.009 ± 0.000	0.023 ± 0.000
FloodModeling2	0.012 ± 0.000	0.019 ± 0.000	0.012 ± 0.001	0.019 ± 0.000
Covid3Month	0.043 ± 0.000	0.043 ± 0.000	0.043 ± 0.000	0.042 ± 0.000
NewsHeadlineSentiment	0.142 ± 0.000	0.142 ± 0.000	0.142 ± 0.000	0.142 ± 0.000
AppliancesEnergy	3.157 ± 0.297	3.455 ± 0.000	3.296 ± 0.280	3.465 ± 0.018
IEEPPG	35.348 ± 0.707	32.892 ± 0.139	35.043 ± 0.982	33.293 ± 0.270

Table 3. Regression RMSE (mean ± std).

5 Conclusions

This study presented the *MF-RingESN*, a memristive-friendly variant of the Echo State Network that integrates memristive dynamics with the minimum-complexity principle inspired by the Simple Cycle Reservoir. The resulting architecture preserves the nonlinear memory mechanisms characteristic of memristive systems while adopting a deterministic and hardware-efficient ring topology.

Experimental analyses across a range of time series classification and regression benchmarks confirmed that MF-RingESN attains comparable or superior predictive accuracy with respect to its conventional (densely connected) counterpart, despite the drastic simplification of the reservoir structure. These findings indicate that structured and deterministic connectivity patterns can effectively replace random initialization in memristive-inspired recurrent models without compromising representational power.

By bridging theoretical parsimony and physical realizability, the proposed approach strengthens the link between neuromorphic principles and reservoir computing. It suggests a viable pathway toward sustainable, scalable, and physically grounded implementations of recurrent neural computation, particularly relevant in energy-constrained or embedded contexts. Future research will ex-

Fig. 1. Critical Difference Plot over the classification tasks.

Fig. 2. Critical Difference Plot over the regression tasks.

plore the deployment of MF-RingESN on real memristive substrates and its integration within broader hardware co-design frameworks for next-generation neuromorphic processors. Moreover, we plan to investigate variants of the model exhibiting non-dissipative [3] or edge-of-stability dynamics [1], as well as modular reservoir architectures [4].

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